

Step-by-step instructions for joint geodetic and gravity models developed in Males and Gottsmann (2021)

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1. 2D Axisymmetric homogeneous models

The following is a set of instructions on how to construct a 2D axisymmetric domain with a homogeneous subsurface to determine variations in the gravitational potential and deformation fields upon magma reservoir recharge, along with the accompanying mass and volume increases within the source. The software utilised is COMSOL Multiphysics v5.4.

- a) Using 'Model Wizard', open a 2D axisymmetric space dimension, adding a 'Solid Mechanics' physics module along with three 'Coefficient Form PDE' modules, as a basic stationary study.
- b) In 'Global Definitions', define the relevant volcanic parameters such as material properties and source parameters, with values utilised in 2D homogeneous models of Erciyes described in Table 1.
- c) Construct a half-space model domain in 'Geometry' (Figure 1):
 - i) Set the default repair tolerance in 'Geometry' and 'Form Union' to 'Relative' with a value of 1E-6.
 - ii) Add a rectangle with its midpoint at $z = 0$ (the free surface), its left axial boundary at $r = 0$ (the symmetrical axis), and of adequate area that interior results remain unaffected by boundary conditions. For Erciyes, the rectangle extends to the depth of the regional Moho (-34 km), with a lateral extent of 80 km, giving the rectangle an area of 80 km * 68 km.
 - iii) Add a circle (or ellipse) with its midpoint at $z = \text{depth}$ and $r = 0$, with a predefined radius. Alter the 'Sector Angle' to 180° and the 'Rotation Angle' to -90° to produce a semicircle with its flat base along the axis of symmetry.
 - iv) Utilising the 'Bezier Polygon' tool, draw a line along $z = 0$, extending from $r = 0$ to the right-hand boundary of the rectangle domain.
- d) Define the material of the domain and source:
 - i) To set the material of the domain, right click on 'Materials' and choose to add a 'Blank Material'. The user-specified choice of Young's

modulus, Poisson's ratio and density, as defined in 'Parameters' may then be applied to the rectangular domain (above and below $z = 0$).

Table 1 – Parameter expressions and values utilised in 2D axisymmetric homogeneous models relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Value	Description
G	$6.67e-11$ [$N \cdot m^2 / kg^2$]	$6.67E-11$ $m^3 / (kg \cdot s^2)$	Gravitational constant
depth	-7000 [m]	-7000 m	Source depth
a	3100 [m]	3100 m	Source radius
V	$4/3 \cdot \pi \cdot a^3$	$1.25E11$ m^3	Source volume
dP	-10 [MPa]	-1E7 Pa	Source boundary pressure
G_s	10 [GPa]	1E10 Pa	Shear modulus
rho_crust	2818 [kg/m^3]	2818 $kg\ m^3$	Crustal density
YM_crust	35.3 [GPa]	3.53E10 Pa	Crustal Young's modulus
Poisson_crust	0.289	0.289	Crustal Poisson's ratio
rho_r1	2500 [kg/m^3]	2500 $kg\ m^3$	Density of the reservoir before mass injection
rho_r2	2510 [kg/m^3]	2510 $kg\ m^3$	Density of the reservoir after mass injection
drho_r	$rho_{r2} - rho_{r1}$	10 $kg\ m^3$	Density change in the reservoir
YM_r	1 [GPa]	1E9 Pa	Reservoir Young's modulus
Poisson_r	0.21	0.21	Reservoir Poisson's ratio

Figure 1 – Schematic diagram of the model domain for an axisymmetric 2D homogeneous model. The model domain is characterised by the material properties defined

in Table 1, and the shaded grey regions highlight the area in which Solid Mechanics model physics are implemented.

- ii) The same method may be followed to define the material of the source, applying user-specified values for the reservoir.
- e) Apply the ‘Solid Mechanics’ physics to the bottom half of the rectangle and the source:
- i) Add a ‘Fixed Constraint’ boundary to the base of the domain to preclude deformation along the bottom of the domain.
 - ii) Add a ‘Roller’ boundary to the right-hand boundary of the domain to inhibit displacement perpendicular of the border.
 - iii) The line along $z = 0$ should automatically be set as ‘Free’ by default.
 - iv) Apply a ‘Boundary Load’ to the peripheral boundaries of the source (not along $r = 0$). Set the ‘Load Type’ to ‘Pressure’ and employ a value of ΔP as defined in ‘Parameters’. Values of ΔP are denoted as negative throughout models due to a notation issue within COMSOL, but do not represent a literal negative change in pressure between the source and the medium.
- f) Apply the first Coefficient Form PDE to the entire model, renaming it ‘Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 1 – Bouguer Slab Term’. This represents the Δg_1 contribution to residual gravity change.
- i) In ‘Units’, modify the ‘Source term quantity’ unit to s^{-2} , with the ‘Dependent variable quantity’ remaining dimensionless.
 - ii) Under the ‘Coefficient Form PDE’ tab, set all the coefficients to zero except for the diffusion coefficient ($c = 1$) and the convection coefficient ($\beta: r = -1/r, z = 0$).
 - iii) Add a ‘Dirichlet Boundary Condition’ to all the peripheral edges of the domain, except for the axis of symmetry ($r = 0$).
 - iv) Add a ‘Source’ condition to the bottom half of the rectangular domain, not including the source, and rename it ‘Source term 1’. Prescribe a source term value of:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G - (d(w * \rho_c, r) + d(w * \rho_c, z)) \quad [1/s^2]$$

where ρ_c represents the density of the crust and f represents the Δg_1 gravity contribution.

g) Apply the second Coefficient Form PDE to the entire model, renaming it 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 2 – Source density changes'. This represents the Δg_2 contribution to residual gravity change.

- i) Follow steps i) – iii) as in 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 1'.
- ii) Add a 'Source' condition to the semi-circle reservoir, renaming it 'Source Term 2 – Magma chamber density change'. Prescribe a source term value of:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G * \Delta\rho \quad [1/s^2]$$

where $\Delta\rho$ represents the change in density of the source before and after mass intrusion and f represents the Δg_2 gravity contribution.

- iii) Add an additional 'Coefficient Form PDE' tab and apply a 'Source Term' (f) condition utilising the same equation as in 1.f.iv to the bottom half of the rectangular domain.

h) Apply the third Coefficient Form PDE to the entire model, renaming it 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 3 – Shifting of crustal density boundaries'. This represents the Δg_3 contribution to residual gravity change.

- i) Follow steps i) to iii) as in 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 1'.
- ii) Add a 'Source' condition to the bottom half of the rectangular domain and the source, renaming it 'Source Term 3 – Crustal density boundaries'. Prescribe a source term value of:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G * \rho_c * -(1/r * d(r * u, r) + d(w, z)) \quad [1/s^2]$$

where f represents the Δg_3 gravity contribution.

i) Create and apply a mesh to the entire domain:

- i) Apply a user-controlled mesh with a shape of choice (default shape is free triangular) in 'Mesh 1'.
- ii) Set the mesh size across the general physics to a magnitude that will permit the computation of accurate displacement and gravity variations across the domain. For Erciyes, maximum and minimum element sizes of 2000 m and 7.5 m are utilised, with a maximum element growth rate of 1.2. A curvature element of 0.25 is applied, along with a resolution of narrow regions value of 1.
- iv) Right click on 'Mesh 1' and add a Free Triangular mesh across the remaining geometric entity levels. Apply a first 'Distribution' to the free surface and outer source boundaries with a fixed number of 60

elements. Apply a second 'Distribution' to just the free surface with a fixed number of 150 elements. These distributions allow resolution to be increased around the source and free surface.

- j) Run the model by right-clicking 'Study 1' and selecting 'Compute'.

These instructions produce a homogeneous 2D axisymmetric model from which gravity field and deformation field variations may be resolved and mass and volume changes at specific source density and boundary pressure changes may be computed.

- k) To produce displacement profiles, a 1D line plot may be created by plotting radial distance (r) against changes in vertical (w), radial, and total displacement (solid.disp). Radial displacement is plotted using the equation:

$$r = \sqrt{(u^2 + v^2)}$$

where u is the eastwards horizontal displacement and v is the northwards horizontal displacement. In 2D models, v is always equal to 0 and thus in 2D, $r = u$.

- l) To create gravity change profiles, 1D line plots may be created by plotting radial distance (r) against the three individual gravity contributions. Gravity contribution terms are multiplied by 1E8 to produce results in μGal .

- m) In order to determine the residual gravity change upon magma reservoir recharge, a 1D line graph is generated by plotting radial distance against the equation for Δg :

$$\Delta g = \Delta g_0 + \Delta g_1 + \Delta g_2 + \Delta g_3$$

where Δg_0 is the free air gradient effect and is accounted for by:

$$\Delta g_0 = w * -0.3086 * 1000 \quad [1/s^2]$$

- n) The resultant mass and volume fluxes to the reservoir may be calculated utilising the analytical solution for source volume change:

$$\Delta V = \frac{\alpha^3 \pi}{\mu} \Delta P$$

where α is the source radius, μ is the shear modulus, and ΔP is the source pressure change. The accompanying mass change may be calculated using the equation:

$$\Delta M = \rho_1 * \Delta V$$

where ρ_1 denotes the initial density of the reservoir before mass intrusion.

2. 2D Axisymmetric heterogeneous models with basic topography

Subsurface mechanical layering and basic topography may be added to the previously described model set up by making a few edits to the geometry, materials and physics sections. Individual coefficient form PDE's representative of the Δg_1 , Δg_2 and Δg_3 gravity contributions must be added for each layer, resulting in a total of 22 coefficient form PDE physics nodes required to represent Erciyes Dağ.

- a) Define new parameter values for the volcanic edifice and mechanical subsurface layers within the crust in 'Parameters'. Values utilised for 2D heterogeneous models of Erciyes may be found in Table 2.
- b) Edit the geometry of the domain (Figure 2):
 - i) Prior to constructing the circle (or ellipse) representing the magma reservoir, add horizontal layers across the width of the rectangular domain at user-specified depths utilising the 'Bezier Polygon' tool.
 - ii) A simple topography may be added by creating a triangular (cone in 3D) shape with the 'Bezier Polygon' tool which represents the volcanic edifice. Erciyes Dağ sits at a prominence of 2800 m and has an average slope angle of 28° , permitting a representative triangle of height 2800 m and width 5260 m to be constructed.
 - iii) The circular source may then be added as in 1.c, with any intersecting segments of depth lines removed by utilising the 'Difference' function. This removes the semi-circle and so another must be added in its place.
- c) Under 'Materials', right-click to add an individual 'Blank Material' node for each depth layer and for the edifice. To assign a 'Material' node to an individual layer, select the relevant domain in 'Geometric entity level'. The respective densities, Young's moduli, and Poisson's ratios of each layer may then be assigned within their corresponding 'Material Contents' sections.
- d) 'Solid Mechanics' model physics are applied in the same manner as in 1.e to the entire domain beneath the free surface, the source, and the volcanic edifice.
- e) Coefficient form PDEs representative of the Δg_1 gravity contribution (Source Term 1) are added individually for each subsurface layer, following the same process as in 1.f. These must be added to the layers individually rather than to the subsurface as a whole due to the discrete changes in density between the boundaries. For Erciyes, seven

Source Term 1 coefficient form PDE physics nodes are added for each of the seven subsurface layers.

Table 2 – Parameter expressions and values utilised in 2D axisymmetric heterogeneous models relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Value	Description
G	$6.67e-11$ [N*m ² /kg ²]	$6.67E-11$ m ³ /(kg*s ²)	Gravitational constant
depth	-7000 [m]	-7000 m	Source depth
a	3100 [m]	3100 m	Source radius
V	$4/3*pi*a^3$	$1.25E11$ m ³	Source volume
dP	-10 [MPa]	-1E7 Pa	Source boundary pressure
G_s	10 [GPa]	1E10 Pa	Shear modulus
rho_crust_edifice	2060 [kg/m ³]	2060 kg m ³	Density of the edifice
rho_crust_layer1	2393 [kg/m ³]	2393 kg m ³	Density of layer 1
rho_crust_layer2	2490 [kg/m ³]	2490 kg m ³	Density of layer 2
rho_crust_layer3	2600 [kg/m ³]	2600 kg m ³	Density of layer 3
rho_crust_layer4	2675 [kg/m ³]	2675 kg m ³	Density of layer 4
rho_crust_layer5	2691 [kg/m ³]	2691 kg m ³	Density of layer 5
rho_crust_layer6	2697 [kg/m ³]	2697 kg m ³	Density of layer 6
rho_crust_layer7	2801 [kg/m ³]	2801 kg m ³	Density of layer 7
rho_r1	2500 [kg/m ³]	2500 kg m ³	Density of the reservoir before mass injection
rho_r2	2510 [kg/m ³]	2510 kg m ³	Density of the reservoir after mass injection
drho_r	$rho_r2 - rho_r1$	10 kg m ³	Density change in the reservoir
YM_r	1 [GPa]	1E9 Pa	Reservoir Young's modulus
Poisson_r	0.21	0.21	Reservoir Poisson's ratio

Figure 2 – Schematic diagram of the model domain for an axisymmetric 2D heterogeneous model. The model domain is characterised by the material properties defined in Table 2, and the shaded grey regions highlight the area in which Solid Mechanics model physics are applied.

- f) Coefficient form PDEs representative of the Δg_2 gravity contribution (Source Term 2) are applied to the reservoir and subsurface in the same manner as in 1.g. Once again, seven Source Term 2 coefficient form PDE nodes are applied to represent the seven subsurface layers of Erciyes.
- g) Coefficient form PDEs representative of the Δg_3 gravity contribution (Source Term 3) are added individually for each subsurface layer, following the same process as in 1.h. For Erciyes, seven Source Term 3 coefficient form PDE physics nodes are added for each of the seven subsurface layers.
- h) The meshing procedure and computation of the simulation may be completed utilising the same approach as before. The creation of gravity variation results requires the individual coefficient form PDEs for each layer to be summed in order to compute the total gravity contribution variations and residual gravity change for the entire domain.

3. 3D Homogeneous models

The following is a set of instructions on how to construct a 3D domain with a homogeneous subsurface in order to determine variations in the deformation and gravitational potential fields upon magma reservoir recharge. From here, the accompanying mass and volume fluxes within the source may also be calculated.

- a) Using 'Model Wizard', open a 3D space dimension, adding a 'Solid Mechanics' physics module along with three 'Coefficient Form PDE' modules, as a basic stationary study.
- b) As in 1., define the relevant volcanic parameters within 'Global Definitions' such as material properties and source parameters, with values utilised for 3D homogeneous models of Erciyes described in Table 3. Values of ΔP are once again denoted as negative in 3D models due to a notation issue within COMSOL.
- c) Construct a 3D domain in 'Geometry' under 'Component 1' (Figure 3):
 - i) Right click on 'Geometry' to add a 'Parametric Surface' (*ps1*). Set the 'First parameter' as 's1' with a minimum value of 0 and maximum value of 1. Set the 'Second parameter' as 's2' with the same minimum and maximum values as s1. In the 'Expressions' tab, set $x = s1*(x_{max} - x_{min})$,

set $y = s^2 \cdot (y_{\max} - y_{\min})$, and set $z = 0$. In the 'Position' tab, locate the parametric surface at coordinates such that the central point of the surface lies at (0,0,0). Apply a relative tolerance and maximum number of knots such that resolution of the final model is adequate but

Table 3 – Parameter expressions and values utilised in 3D homogeneous models relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Value	Description
G	$6.67e-11 \text{ [N*m}^2/\text{kg}^2]$	$6.67E-11 \text{ m}^3/(\text{kg*s}^2)$	Gravitational constant
depth	-7000 [m]	-7000 m	Source depth
a	3100 [m]	3100 m	Source radius
V	$4/3 \cdot \pi \cdot a^3$	$1.25E11 \text{ m}^3$	Source volume
dP	-10 [MPa]	-1E7 Pa	Source boundary pressure
G_s	10 [GPa]	1E10 Pa	Shear modulus
rho_crust	2818 [kg/m ³]	2818 kg m ³	Crustal density
YM_crust	35.3 [GPa]	3.53E10 Pa	Crustal Young's modulus
Poisson_crust	0.289	0.289	Crustal Poisson's ratio
rho_r1	2500 [kg/m ³]	2500 kg m ³	Density of the reservoir before mass injection
rho_r2	2510 [kg/m ³]	2510 kg m ³	Density of the reservoir after mass injection
drho_r	$\text{rho_r2} - \text{rho_r1}$	10 kg m ³	Density change in the reservoir
YM_r	1 [GPa]	1E9 Pa	Reservoir Young's modulus
Poisson_r	0.21	0.21	Reservoir Poisson's ratio

Figure 3 – Schematic diagram of the model domain for a 3D homogeneous model. The model domain is characterised by the material properties defined in Table 3, and the shaded grey regions highlight the area in which Solid Mechanics model physics are employed.

computational cost is not too large. For Erciyes Dağ, a relative tolerance of 0.001 and maximum number of knots 150 were utilised.

- ii) Add a 'Block' (*blk1*) with width, depth, and height dimensions relating to the size of the required domain. For Erciyes, a width and depth of 80 km are utilised, with a height of 68 km, comparable to the 2D axisymmetric model domain areas. Position the base according to its corner, with coordinates of (0,0,z), such that the z value results in half the domain lying above $z = 0$, and half lying below.
 - iii) Right-click on 'Geometry' and choose 'Convert to Solid' (*csol1*) within the 'Conversions' tab. Select *ps1* and *blk1* and choose 'Build selected' to convert them to a solid.
 - iv) Right-click on 'Geometry' and select 'Delete Entities', highlighting the area of the *csol1* domain above $z = 0$ and choose 'Build Selected'. This will leave the bottom half of the *csol1* domain as a remainder.
 - v) Create an identical parametric surface (*ps2*) to *ps1*, utilising the same expressions and locating it in the same position, with *ps2* effectively lying directly on top of *ps1*.
 - vi) Add another 'Block' (*blk2*) with dimensions identical to *blk1*. This time, however, position the base corner z-coordinate 2 km higher than in *blk1*, shifting *blk2* up by 2 km.
 - vii) Convert *ps2* and *blk2* to solid utilising the 'Convert to Solid' node (*csol2*) as before. Then, using 'Delete Entities', erase the bottom half of *csol2*. This will result in a final domain comprised of the bottom half of *csol1* and the top half of *csol2*.
 - viii) A sphere (or ellipsoid) representing the magmatic reservoir may now be added. Define the radius and depth of the sphere using the values defined in 'Parameters'. Position the sphere at x and y coordinates appropriate for the user-specified choice of source location. Ensure the 'Axis type' is set to spherical, with theta and phi values of 90° .
- d) Materials may now be applied to the different domains using the same methods as in 1.d. Values utilised in 3D homogeneous models of Erciyes are described in Table 3.

- e) Solid Mechanics model physics may be applied in the same way as in 1.e, with ‘Roller’ boundaries applied to the peripheral borders of the domain beneath the free surface, a ‘Fixed Constraint’ added to the base of the model, and a ‘Boundary Load’ pressure applied to the source.
- f) As in 1.f, the first Coefficient Form PDE representative of the Δg_1 gravity variation contribution is assigned as ‘Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 1 – Bouguer Slab Term’.
- i) Apply the PDE to the entire domain, with Dirichlet Boundary Conditions set to every external face of the domain.
 - ii) Within the Coefficient Form PDE coefficient values, set every coefficient to 0, excluding the diffusion coefficient (c) which is set to 1.
 - v) Add a ‘Source’ term node, applying it to all domains beneath the free surface. Set the Source Term equation (f) to:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G * -(d(u2 * \rho_c, x) + d(\nu2 * \rho_c, y) + d(w2 * \rho_c, z))$$
- g) The second Coefficient Form PDE representative of the Δg_2 gravity variation contribution is assigned as ‘Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 2 – Source Density Changes’.
- i) Apply the ‘Coefficient Form PDE 1’ node within the general Coefficient Form PDE to only the source and upper half of the cuboid domain, with coefficient values within this all set to 0, except c which is equal to 1.
 - ii) An additional ‘Coefficient Form PDE 2’ node must be added and applied to the lower half of the cuboid domain. Within ‘Coefficient Form PDE 2’, the diffusion coefficient (c) and damping coefficient (d_a) are set to 1, and the Source Term (f) is set to the same equation as in 3.f. Set all the remaining terms to 0 and apply Dirichlet Boundary Conditions to the external faces of the domain.
 - iii) Apply a ‘Source’ term to the source reservoir alone, using the same equation as in 1.g.
- h) As in 1.h, the third Coefficient Form PDE representative of the Δg_3 gravity variation contribution is assigned as ‘Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 3 – Shifting of Crustal Density Boundaries’.
- i) Apply the PDE to the entire domain, with Dirichlet Boundary Conditions set to every external face of the domain.

- ii) Set every value within the Coefficient Form PDE coefficient values to 0, excluding the diffusion coefficient (c) which is set to 1.
- iii) Add a 'Source' term node, applying it to all domains beneath the free surface, and set the equation as:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G * \rho_c * -(d(u2, x) + d(v2, y)d(w2, z))$$

- i) A mesh may now be applied to the domain through the following steps:
 - i) Set the 'Sequence Type' to 'User-controlled mesh'. Within the 'Size' node, calibrate the 'General physics' to the predefined 'Fine' element size setting.
 - ii) Right-click on 'Mesh' and add a 'Free Tetrahedral' node. Change the Geometric entity level to 'Remaining'. Within 'Control Entities' set the number of iterations and maximum element depth to values required to produce the necessary resolution.
- j) Run the model by right-clicking 'Study 1' and selecting 'Compute'.

These instructions produce a homogeneous 3D model from which gravitational potential and deformation field variations may be resolved and mass and volume changes at specific source density and boundary pressure changes may be computed. Results plots may be generated following the instructions described in 1.

4. 3D Heterogeneous layered models

The following describes instructions on how to construct a 3D domain with a heterogeneous, discretely layered subsurface. The real 3D topography of the region is also accounted for. This will permit the determination of more accurate variations in the deformation and gravitational potential fields upon magma reservoir recharge and the accompanying values for mass and volume fluxes into the source. Individual coefficient form PDE's representative of the Δg_1 , Δg_2 and Δg_3 gravity contributions must be added for each layer, resulting in a total of 24 coefficient form PDE physics nodes required to represent Erciyes Dağ.

- a) Utilising 'Model Wizard', open a 3D space dimension, adding a 'Solid Mechanics' physics module along with 24 'Coefficient Form PDE' modules, as a basic stationary study.

- b) As in 2, define the relevant volcanic parameters within 'Global Definitions' such as material properties and source parameters. The values utilised for 3D heterogeneous layered models of Erciyes are described in Table 4. Similarly to 3, values of (ΔP) must be denoted as negative.

Right-click on 'Global Definitions' and within the 'Functions' tab select 'Interpolation' (*int1*). Change the 'Data source' to 'File' and browse for the relevant digital elevation model (DEM) file within your saved documents and import it into COMSOL. Ensure that 'Interpolation' is set to 'Linear' and that 'Extrapolation' is set to 'Constant' and finally select 'Create Plot'.

Table 4 – Parameter expressions and values utilised in 3D heterogeneous layered models relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Value	Description
G	$6.67e-11 \text{ [N*m}^2/\text{kg}^2]$	6.67E-11 $\text{m}^3/(\text{kg*s}^2)$	Gravitational constant
depth	-7000 [m]	-7000 m	Source depth
a	3100 [m]	3100 m	Source radius
V	$4/3*\pi*a^3$	1.25E11 m^3	Source volume
dP	-10 [MPa]	-1E7 Pa	Source boundary pressure
G_s	10 [GPa]	1E10 Pa	Shear modulus
rho_crust_edifice	2060 [kg/m ³]	2060 kg m^3	Density of the edifice
rho_crust_layer1	2393 [kg/m ³]	2393 kg m^3	Density of layer 1
rho_crust_layer2	2490 [kg/m ³]	2490 kg m^3	Density of layer 2
rho_crust_layer3	2600 [kg/m ³]	2600 kg m^3	Density of layer 3
rho_crust_layer4	2675 [kg/m ³]	2675 kg m^3	Density of layer 4
rho_crust_layer5	2691 [kg/m ³]	2691 kg m^3	Density of layer 5
rho_crust_layer6	2697 [kg/m ³]	2697 kg m^3	Density of layer 6
rho_crust_layer7	2801 [kg/m ³]	2801 kg m^3	Density of layer 7
rho_r1	2500 [kg/m ³]	2500 kg^3	Density of the reservoir before mass injection
rho_r2	2501 [kg/m ³]	2510 kg m^3	Density of the reservoir after mass injection
drho_r	$\text{rho}_r2 - \text{rho}_r1$	1 kg m^3	Density change in the reservoir
YM_r	1 [GPa]	1E9 Pa	Reservoir Young's modulus
Poisson_r	0.21	0.21	Reservoir Poisson's ratio

Figure 4 – Schematic diagram of the model domain for a 3D heterogeneous model with discrete subsurface layers. The model domain is characterised by the material properties defined in Table 4, and the shaded grey regions highlight the area in which Solid Mechanics model physics are employed.

c) Construct the 3D domain within 'Geometry' (Figure 4):

- i) To implement the real 3D topography of the region, add a 'Parametric Surface' within Geometry. Set the first and second parameter names and values, as well as the expressions for x and y in the same manner as in 3.c.i. For the z expression, set the value to:

$$z = \text{int1}(s1*(x_{\max}-x_{\min})+x_{\min}, s2*(y_{\max}-y_{\min})+y_{\min})$$

where *int1* represents the interpolation surface. Set the 'Position' coordinates, the 'Relative tolerance' and the 'Maximum number of knots' in the same manner as in 3.c.i.

- ii) Follow steps ii) – vii) as described in 3.c. This will result in the production of the cuboid domain and topographic surface to be utilised throughout the 3D heterogeneous layered model.
- iii) Add a sphere (or ellipsoid) representative of the magmatic reservoir, defining the radius and depth of the sphere using the values defined in 'Parameters' (Table 4). Position the sphere at x and y coordinates appropriate for the user-specified choice of source location. Set the 'Axis type' is to z-type, with a 'Rotation' of 0°.

- vi) Implement parametric surfaces at relevant depths illustrative of the boundaries between the subsurface mechanical layers. For Erciyes, seven subsurface depth layers are present, requiring the addition of 6 parametric surfaces beneath the topographic surface.
 - vii) In order to represent the volcanic edifice, a 'Cylinder' must be added by right-clicking 'Geometry'. Set a 'Radius', 'Height', and 'Position' of the cylinder such that the entire volcanic edifice is encompassed, situated with its base at the depth of the surrounding plateau.
 - viii) Right-click on 'Geometry' and within 'Conversions' choose 'Convert to Solid'. Select all domains beneath the topographic surface as well as the cylinder and topographic surface itself, but excluding the spherical reservoir.
 - ix) Following this, select 'Delete Entities' within the 'Geometry' tab, and highlight all areas of the cylinder which are present above the topographic surface. This will delete these areas, resulting in a cylinder which extends only below the topographic surface to the depth of the surrounding plateau.
 - x) Right-click on 'Geometry' and within 'Conversions' choose 'Convert to Solid'. Highlight the sphere and choose 'Build Selected'.
 - ix) Right-click on 'Geometry' and within the 'More Primitives' tab, add a 'Point' to the domain. Position the point such that it lies directly on topographic parametric surface at the centre of the volcanic edifice. This point will be utilised during the meshing procedure.
- d) Apply 'Materials' to each of the individual subsurface layers in the same manner as described in 2.c.
- e) The 'Solid Mechanics' model physics may be applied to every domain beneath the topographic surface in the same method as in 3.e.
- f) Denote the first group of 8 Coefficient Form PDEs, representative of the Δg_1 gravity variation contributions, as 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 1 – Bouguer Slab Term'. Following the method described in 3.k, apply each PDE to every individual subsurface layer, including the cylinder representing the edifice. Apply the Source Term equation:

$$f = -4 * \pi * G * -(d(w * \rho_l, x) + d(w * \rho_l, y) + d(w * \rho_l, z))$$

to each distinct subsurface layer, with ρ_i representing the discrete density of the individual layers.

- g) Denote the second group of 8 Coefficient Form PDEs, representative of the Δg_2 gravity variation contributions, as 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 2 – Source Density Changes'. Following the method described in 3.l, apply the PDEs to every individual subsurface layer, including the cylinder representing the edifice. Ensure the Source Term equation within Coefficient Form PDE 2 node is the same as that described in 4.g, with appropriate densities for the relevant layers utilised within the equation.
- h) Denote the final group of 8 Coefficient Form PDEs, representative of the Δg_3 gravity variation contributions, as 'Coefficient Form PDE: Source Term 3 – Shifting of Crustal Density Boundaries'. Following the method described in 3.m, apply the PDEs to each individual subsurface layer, including the cylinder representing the edifice. Ensure the PDE for each layer utilises the relevant density of that layer within the 'Source Term' equations and replace the u^2 , v^2 and w^2 terms by u , v and w respectively.
- i) A 'User-controlled mesh' may now be implemented:
 - i) Within 'Size', set the 'Calibrate for' tab to 'General physics' and set the element size to 'Normal'.
 - ii) Add an additional 'Size' node, this time selecting 'Point' as the 'geometric entity level'. Highlight the Point on the topographic surface that was added in constructing the geometry of the domain. Set the 'Element Size' to 'Custom' and define appropriate element size parameters in order to produce a high-resolution mesh surrounding the point. For Erciyes, a maximum and minimum element size of 20 m and 5 m are applied, with a maximum element growth rate of 1.1 and a curvature factor of 0.4.
 - iii) Add a further 'Size' node and apply it to the cylinder domain representing the volcanic edifice. Set the 'Element Size' to 'Normal' and click 'Build All'.
- j) Run the model by right-clicking 'Study 1' and selecting 'Compute'.

These instructions produce a discretely layered heterogeneous 3D model from which more accurate gravity field and deformation field variations may be resolved and mass and volume

changes at specific source density and boundary pressure changes may be computed. Plots of results may be generated following the instructions described in 2.

5. 3D Heterogeneous non-layered models

The following describes instructions on how to construct a 3D, topographically influenced domain composed of a heterogeneous, non-layered subsurface with gradually changing mechanical properties. By modelling the crust using a single material governed by gradually varying density, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio values, a faster to create and less computationally expensive model may be produced. Because only a single material is utilised for the crust, with just one other material applied to the edifice, only 2 coefficient form PDE's are required for each of the individual gravity contributions, resulting in a total of just 6 PDE nodes required to represent Erciyes Dağ within the 3D heterogeneous non-layered model.

- a) Prior to constructing the model on COMSOL, density, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio data must first be fit to polynomial equations in MATLAB. For Erciyes, third order polynomial equations were fit to Young's modulus and density data, whereas a quartic polynomial equation was fitted to the Poisson's ratio data in order to produce a best-fit graph.
- b) Utilising 'Model Wizard', open a 3D space dimension, adding a 'Solid Mechanics' physics module along with 6 'Coefficient Form PDE' modules as a basic stationary study.
- c) Within 'Global Definitions', define the relevant volcanic parameters and source parameters. Unlike other models, do not add the crustal density values to the Parameters section, these will be added in the next step. The values utilised for 3D heterogeneous non-layered models of Erciyes are described in Table 5.
- d) Within 'Component', right-click on 'Definitions' and add a 'Variables' node. The three polynomial equations that were formulated in MATLAB may be copied and pasted into Variables and units may be added. The polynomial equations relevant to Erciyes Dağ are displayed in Table 6.
- e) From here, construct a model domain following the steps outlined in 4.c - 4d.iii (Figure 5).

- f) After the domain and spherical chamber have been constructed, finish constructing the geometry and follow the instructions described in 4.d.iv – 4.f.
- g) After the domain and spherical chamber have been constructed, finish constructing the geometry and follow the instructions described in 10.4.d.iv – 10.4.f.
- h) Apply discrete Coefficient Form PDEs representative of the three gravity contribution terms to the volcanic edifice and crustal domain following the same methods as in 10.4.g – 10.4.i.
- i) Apply a ‘User-controlled’ Mesh with ‘Normal’ Element Size to the Remaining General Physics of the model. Then add an additional ‘Size’ node and select ‘Point’ within ‘Geometric entity level’. Highlight the Point added to the surface within the geometry construction and apply a Custom Element Size as appropriate to produce high-resolution results around the volcanic edifice. The Element Size Parameters utilised for Erciyes are described in 10.4.j.
- j) Run the model by right-clicking ‘Study 1’ and selecting ‘Compute’.

These instructions produce a heterogeneous 3D model in which material properties vary gradually throughout the crust according to third order polynomial equations. This permits a model with reduced computational cost to be constructed, providing an alternative geodetic and gravimetric end-member solution to the discretely layered heterogeneous 3D model constructed in 4. Plots of results may be generated following the instructions described in 2.

Table 5 – Parameter expressions and values utilised in 3D heterogeneous non-layered models relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Value	Description
G	$6.67e-11 \text{ [N*m}^2\text{/kg}^2\text{]}$	$6.67E-11 \text{ m}^3\text{/(kg*s}^2\text{)}$	Gravitational constant
depth	-7000 [m]	-7000 m	Source depth
a	3100 [m]	3100 m	Source radius
V	$4/3*\pi*a^3$	$1.25E11 \text{ m}^3$	Source volume
dP	-10 [MPa]	$-1E7 \text{ Pa}$	Source boundary pressure
G_s	10 [GPa]	$1E10 \text{ Pa}$	Shear modulus
rho_crust_edifice	$2060 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}$	2060 kg m^3	Density of the edifice
rho_r1	$2500 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}$	2500 kg m^3	Density of the reservoir before mass injection
rho_r2	$2501 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}$	2510 kg m^3	Density of the reservoir after mass injection
drho_r	$\text{rho_r2} - \text{rho_r1}$	1 kg m^3	Density change in the reservoir

YM_r	1 [GPa]	1E9 Pa	Reservoir Young's modulus
Poisson_r	0.21	0.21	Reservoir Poisson's ratio

Table 6 – Variable expressions of the polynomial equations for Young's modulus, density and Poisson's ratio data relevant to Erciyes Dağ.

Name	Expression	Unit	Description
YM_crust	$21545743525.8774 \text{ [Pa]} - 3683775.6011 \text{ [Pa/m}^2\text{]} * z \text{ [m]} - 198.2781 \text{ [Pa/m}^4\text{]} * z^2 \text{ [m}^2\text{]} - 0.0035027 \text{ [Pa/m}^6\text{]} * z^3 \text{ [m}^3\text{]}$	Pa	Third order polynomial equation for the Young's modulus of the crust
rho_crust	$2467.0919 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]} - 0.074461 \text{ [kg/m}^5\text{]} * z \text{ [m]} - 4.4583e-6 \text{ [kg/m}^7\text{]} * z^2 \text{ [m}^2\text{]} - 7.5442e-11 \text{ [kg/m}^9\text{]} * z^3 \text{ [m}^3\text{]}$	kg m ³	Third order polynomial equation for the density of the crust
Poisson_crust	$0.19444 \text{ [1]} - 3.5845e-5 \text{ [1/m}^2\text{]} * z \text{ [m]} - 4.1554e-9 \text{ [1/m}^4\text{]} * z^2 \text{ [m}^2\text{]} - 1.628e-13 \text{ [1/m}^6\text{]} * z^3 \text{ [m}^3\text{]} - 1.9965e-18 \text{ [1/m}^8\text{]} * z^4 \text{ [m}^4\text{]}$	-	Quartic polynomial equation for the Poisson's ratio of the crust

Figure 5 – Schematic diagram of the model domain for a 3D heterogeneous model with gradually varying mechanical properties. The model domain is characterised by the material properties defined in Table 5 and Table 6, and the shaded grey regions highlight the area in which Solid Mechanics model physics are employed.